

Optical properties of sonochemically synthesized dysprosium doped CdO nanoparticles[†]

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Abstract : The undoped and dysprosium-doped CdO nanoparticles were prepared by sonochemical method in aqueous media and characterized with X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectrum, and photoluminescence spectra. The results of XRD indicated that the obtained CdO : Dy³⁺ nanoparticles were well crystallized with a cubic phase. The TEM image illustrated that the CdO : Dy³⁺ nanoparticles were spherical with an average size around 40 nm. Under irradiation of UV light, the emission spectrum of CdO : Dy³⁺ nanoparticles exhibited alongwith the host emission, the characteristic line emissions arising from the ⁴F_{9/2} → ⁶H_J (*J* = 13/2, 15/2) transitions of the Dy³⁺ ions, with the dominating emission centered at ~580 nm. The optimum doping concentration for CdO : Dy³⁺ nanoparticles was determined to be 3 mol%.

Keywords : CdO, nanoparticle, dysprosium dopant, sonochemical synthesis, photoluminescence studies.

Introduction

The synthesis and characterization of oxide and sulfide nanoparticles have been active areas of investigations during the past two decades because of the novel properties of the nanoparticles compared to those of their bulk counterparts. A key aspect of the rapidly developing area of nanoscience and nanotechnology concerns itself with the size dependence of intrinsic properties of the materials. Studies on these types of materials will lead to new devices and technology. For example, the resolution of images on a cathode ray display tube is closely related to the particle size of phosphors. In general, smaller the particles the better will be the resolution. Phosphors in the micrometre size (4–8 μm) regime, used extensively in a conventional colour television set, are not suitable for high-definition television¹. It is now established that doped semiconductor nanoparticles formed a new class of luminescent materials for various applications. The quantum confinement effect of nanoparticles leads to an increase in the bandgap, causing the edges of the bands to split into discrete energy levels^{2,3}.

CdO, a *n*-type II–VI semiconductor, is a promising candidate for various applications such as photovoltaic

cells⁴, transparent electrodes⁵, photo-transistors⁶, photodiodes⁷ and gas sensors⁸ due to its high electrical conductivity and high optical transmittance in the visible region of the solar spectrum along with a moderate refractive index. It is a direct band gap (2.5 eV) semiconductor, with an indirect band gap of 1.98 eV^{9–12}. Nanostructured CdO is particularly interesting because it can serve as an electrode for nanoscale light-emitting diodes, lasers, and can also be applied in other devices^{11,13}. Consequently, a variety of techniques have been explored for the synthesis of nano CdO which includes surfactant¹⁴, micro emulsion^{15,16}, CVD¹⁷, electrodeposition¹⁸, vapor transport¹⁹ and also sonochemical methods²⁰.

Generally, rare earth ions like Eu³⁺, Er³⁺ and so forth are incorporated in semiconductors to improve the luminescence efficiency by energy transfer process. The optical properties of rare earth ions trapped in host lattices have received much attention in terms of fundamental and technological importance²¹. These matrices effectively reduce the quenching of surface rare earth emission by shielding the rare earth ions present on the surface of the nanoparticles from the external ligands. However, there are very few reports on rare earth ion doped

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

CdO nanoparticles and to the best of our knowledge, none on dysprosium doped CdO nanoparticles. In view of this, we have synthesized nearly monodispersed CdO nanoparticles and also Dy³⁺ doped CdO nanoparticles with a narrow size distribution using a sonochemical technique. The nanoparticles have been characterized thoroughly, and their optical properties have also been investigated. Results of this work are reported herein.

Experimental

All the reactions were carried out at room temperature under ambient conditions. High purity cadmium iodide (CdI₂) and dysprosium nitrate [Dy(NO₃)₃·6H₂O] were obtained from commercial sources (Aldrich). AR grade ammonia solution was used.

Preparation of cadmium oxide nanoparticles :

In a typical reaction procedure, CdI₂ (2 g, 5.46 mmol) was taken in a standard 100 ml beaker and 60 ml of double distilled water was added to it. The solution was made basic by drop-wise addition of ammonia (1 ml). It was then irradiated with a high intensity ultrasonic (100 W cm⁻²) radiation operating at 20 kHz, under air at room temperature for 2 h. After sonication, the precipitate was first washed with water and subsequently centrifuged. The white powder obtained was dried and heated in a furnace under nitrogen at 475 °C for 2 h. The resulting orange yellow colored residue was collected and stored in clean plastic vials.

Preparation of dysprosium doped cadmium oxide nanoparticles :

CdO doped with 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 mol% Dy³⁺ ions were also synthesized. The method is similar to that reported for cadmium oxide nanoparticles, but here a stoichiometric amount of dysprosium nitrate was also added to the reaction mixture.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were carried out on a Philips instrument, operating with Cu-K_α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5417 \text{ \AA}$) and employing a scan rate of 0.02°/s in the scattering angular range (2θ) 20–80°. The average crystallite size was calculated from the diffraction line width based on the Scherrer relation : $d = 0.9\lambda / B \cos \theta$, where λ is the wavelength of X-rays and B is the half-maximum line width. The instrumental broadening was corrected using standard silicon sample. Conventional TEM was recorded on JEOL 2000FX. The particulates obtained were dispersed in methanol solution and then deposited on the carbon-coated copper grids for TEM studies. X-Ray photoelectron spectra (XPS) were recorded

using Mg-K_α radiation (1253.6 eV) on VG Microtech FISON instrument. Diffuse reflectance UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a JASCO spectrometer using an integrating sphere accessory. All luminescence measurements were carried out at room temperature with a resolution of 3 nm, using a Hitachi instrument (F-4500) having a 150 W Xe lamp as the excitation source. Powder samples (5 mg) were mixed with methanol, spread over a quartz plate, dried at 100 °C and mounted inside the sample chamber for photoluminescence measurements.

Results and discussion

The diffraction pattern of the undoped CdO is shown in Fig. 1a, which matches with the cubic phase of CdO, with lattice parameter of $a = 4.6950 \text{ \AA}$. This is in good agreement with that reported in literature (JCPDS No. 05-0640). For all the doped samples, similar powder XRD patterns were obtained and a representative pattern for doped CdO : Dy (3%) particles is shown in Fig. 1b. The XRD patterns indicate that the well-crystallized CdO crys-

Fig 1. XRD patterns of (a) undoped and (b) doped CdO : Dy³⁺.

tals can be easily obtained under the current synthetic conditions. The average crystalline domain, as calculated from the XRD line widths using Scherrer's equation, is

~35 nm for undoped CdO and between 35 to 45 nm for all the doped CdO nanoparticles. The size of particles are much less than that reported earlier by the reaction of $\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) using a sonochemical method²⁰. The following reaction is proposed to explain the mechanism behind the formation of CdO nanoparticles.

OH^- ions formed as a result of the reaction of H_2O with NH_3 . Cadmium ions then react with it and CdO nuclei forms rapidly under the reaction conditions. Suslick²² reported that there are three regions of sonochemical activity : (i) the inside of the collapsing bubble ($T > 5000$ K), (ii) the interface between the bubble and liquid ($T \approx 1900$ K) and (iii) the bulk solution which is at ambient temperature. We propose that the formation of CdO occurs at the interfacial region. On increasing the ultrasonic irradiation time from 2 to 3 h, initial crystal growth stage of CdO nanoparticles could be discerned. The structure and morphology of the above particles have been further analyzed by TEM. Fig. 2a and 2c show the bright field TEM image of the CdO and CdO : Dy particles. The undoped CdO nanoparticles are spherical and have a mean

Fig. 2. (a) TEM image, (b) SAED pattern of undoped CdO and (c) TEM image of doped CdO : Dy^{3+} .

diameter of 35 nm along with a standard deviation of 2.9 nm. The doped particles have an average diameter of 40 nm with a standard deviation of 5 nm. This is in excellent agreement to the size obtained from the XRD line broadening method for the same samples. The addition of dopants does not lead to any change in the morphology of the particles compared to the undoped particles. The corresponding SAED pattern of the nanoparticles, as shown in Fig. 2b, confirmed its crystalline nature. The diffraction rings corresponding to the (200), (111), (220) planes

are clearly visible in the SAED pattern. The interplanar spacing calculated from selected area electron diffraction patterns agrees well with that reported (JCPDS No. 05-0640).

Further evidence for the quality and composition of the doped nanoparticles was obtained from XPS studies. XPS survey spectrum of CdO : Dy (3%) is shown in Fig. 3. In the spectrum, it can be seen that the Cd 3d region in CdO consists of the main $3d_{3/2}$ spin-orbit com-

Fig. 3. XPS survey spectrum of CdO : Dy^{3+} .

ponents at binding energies of 404 and 412 eV, respectively. The binding energy for oxygen is found to be 530 eV which corresponds to oxide formation. Dy^{3+} peaks were observed at 152.5 eV which matches well with that reported in literature²³. The quantification of the peaks yielded a ratio of Cd/O/Dy in the range 0.968 : 1.053 : 0.032, which is in good agreement with the values obtained from elemental analysis of the nanoparticles.

The optical properties of the undoped and doped CdO nanoparticles were characterized. Fig. 4a gives a reflective UV-Vis absorption spectrum of the undoped CdO nanoparticles. To further determine the band gap of these nanoparticles, a plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs $h\nu$ is shown in the inset of Fig. 4a. The band gap of the undoped CdO nanoparticles obtained was ~3.9 eV. The reported value for the direct band gap of bulk CdO is 2.5 eV. The large blue shift of ~1.4 eV of the direct band gap can be explained by the quantum confinement effect²⁴⁻²⁶. Fig. 4b shows the photoluminescence spectrum of these CdO nanoparticles excited at 360 nm. An emission peak at ~519 nm was recorded, which arises from the combination of the electrons from the conduction band and holes from the va-

lence band. It was reported that depending on particle sizes and exciting wavelengths, the different emission peaks and shapes could be seen in the range of 400–600 nm^{26,27}. The excitation spectrum (Fig. 4c) was obtained at the emission wavelength of 520 nm, which shows an intrinsic excitation at 360 nm.

Fig. 4. (a) Reflective UV-Vis absorption spectrum of the undoped CdO nanoparticles. The inset shows a plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs $h\nu$ for the determination of the direct band gap of the nanoparticles, (b) photoluminescence emission spectrum of the CdO nanoparticles excited at 360 nm and (c) excitation spectra of the CdO nanoparticles.

The luminescence properties of CdO doped with different molar ratios of Dy³⁺ ions were also investigated. The corresponding PL spectrum for the 3% Dy doped CdO sample when excited at 360 nm is shown in Fig. 5. Apart from the emission at 519 nm from the CdO host, the emission spectra in all cases are dominated by two

Fig. 5. Emission spectra of 3% doped CdO : Dy³⁺.

main peaks, the strongest one in the yellow region centered at ~578 nm corresponding to the ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$ transition and a less strong one in the blue region centered at ~480 nm corresponding to the ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{15/2}$ transition in Dy³⁺¹⁶. With respect to dysprosium, the ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{15/2}$ transition is mainly magnetically allowed and varies insignificantly with the crystal field strength around the dysprosium ion. On the other hand, the ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$ transition is a forced electric dipole transition being al-

Fig. 6. Effect of Dy³⁺ concentration on the emission intensity of the ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$ transition of Dy³⁺ ions in CdO : Dy³⁺ samples.

lowed only at low symmetries with no inversion center. The ratio between the electric dipole and the magnetic dipole is a measure of the site symmetry in which the dysprosium situated. When the Dy^{3+} ion is located at a low-symmetry local site (without an inversion center), this emission transition is often prominent in its emission spectra²⁸. In our case, due to the size mismatch between Dy^{3+} and Cd^{2+} ions, the excess Dy^{3+} ions will most likely reside on the surface or on the grain boundaries of the nanocrystals to yield optimum strain relaxation. Therefore, situated at such low-symmetry local sites for Dy^{3+} ions, the ${}^4F_{9/2}$ - ${}^6H_{13/2}$ transition emission may show up prominently in the emission spectra.

The effect of Dy^{3+} concentration (in mol%) on the emission intensities of $Cd_{1-x}Dy_xO$ was also studied. The corresponding relative emission intensities of the ${}^4F_{9/2}$ - ${}^6H_{13/2}$ transition of Dy^{3+} ions in CdO samples doped with different molar ratios of Dy^{3+} ions is shown in Fig. 6. It can be observed that the maximum intensity is at 3 mol% doping of Dy^{3+} . The emission intensity rises till a doping concentration of 3 mol% but then it decreases to almost nothing at 5 mol%. The decrease in emission intensity is due to the concentration quenching effect at higher doping concentration²⁹. As mentioned above, on introducing more Dy^{3+} ions into the CdO host, only a minor portion of Dy^{3+} ions would go into the Cd substitutional positions, most may be absorbed at the surface of the nanocrystalline CdO or form a second phase, which offers much more opportunity for the cross-relaxation processes.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we have successfully synthesized undoped CdO and CdO : Dy^{3+} nanoparticles by means of a sonochemical technique. The structural properties of these phosphors have been investigated by XRD and TEM measurements. The composition has been verified using XPS. The luminescence properties of undoped CdO and CdO : Dy^{3+} nanophosphors have been studied by measurement of their excitation and emission spectra. The emission spectra show two bands in the blue (${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{15/2}$) and yellow (${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$) regions, dominated by the Dy^{3+} ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$ hypersensitive transition. Experimental results revealed that the luminescence intensity is affected by concentration of Dy^{3+} in the CdO host. Optimum concentration of Dy^{3+} was found to be 3 mol% of Cd^{2+} in the host lattices. Such a brightly lumi-

nescent phosphor could be considered as an ideal optical material for the development of new optical display systems.

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